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DEVELOPMENT OF PROPORTIONAL LOAD SHARING FOR POWER SYSTEMS WITH VARIED GENERATION CAPABILITIES

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***Abstract:** Modern power systems that have distributed and diverse sources of generation require effective load balancing for optimum operations and system stability. In this paper, load sharing is analyzed with emphasis on proportional load balancing among generators with different ratings. The paper presents a thorough case study of proportional load sharing in a multi-generator environment. A simulation model is created in Python using Tkinter to illustrate how generators actually participate in foisting varying loads and demand on the system according to their rating. The interface allows users to change the values of generator capacities and the extent of the network so that the behavior of the system can be monitored immediately. The results obtained verify that in systems with appropriate supporting generators, power distribution, and proportional load sharing, overloading is avoided.*

***Key Words:** Load Sharing, Droop Control, Generators, Power System.*

1. Introduction

The term load sharing can be defined as the use of multiple generators or power sources to supply a particular power rated demand. Each power source has the ability to stand independently on its own and generate the required power [1-4]. The complexities incorporated in a power system because of the inclusion of both conventional and renewable systems increases the need for the algorithmic mechanisms of load sharing in order to ensure stability, reliability and optimal power generation performance. This paper examines load sharing with regards to different power generation systems, with emphasis on both fossil fuel based power plants and distributed renewable energy systems. The integration of smart grid systems, energy storage devices and hybrid power systems are fundamental in dealing with the issues related to load sharing in robust power generation systems. Power reliability and effective transmission lies at the core of every modern civilization in the world today. With regard to power, the term electrical load sharing refers to the division of electrical energy meant for supply during a given period of time utilized by several generators, or other power sources in order to achieve some optimal balance of the offered demand. More so, with multiple power generating units operating in parallel such as diesel generators, gas turbines, renewable energy sources, and others, the system's electricity demands along with various load requirements are achieved without overtaxing any part of the power grid system. To prevent power overloads and guarantee reliable power supply, raised principles of load sharing systematically control electrical demand to the number of operational generators and their capability to function. Load sharing is the coordination of both active and reactive power management. For work to be done, active power is employed while reactive power is used to sustain voltage levels as well as energy transfer with source frequency and voltage control. In interconnected power systems, dependable system frequency and voltage levels enhances system stability. Load sharing ensures generators proportionately contribute to demand allowing regulation of these parameters. There are three approaches to load sharing. First method is Droop Control and is the one most targeted for sharing between generators [5-10]. This technique allocates one frequency to a generator's output that is relative to its load. This allows all connected

generators to proportionally reduce frequency to an extent which enables yoga to be distributed automatically with increased load. Second mode is Isochronous Load Sharing [11, 12]. One auxiliary generator operates on isochronous mode (constant frequency), while the others work in droop mode. This practice is common in smaller systems or isolated grids where one generator has to take the role of keeping the system frequency stable while the other generators just follow the changes in the load. The third method is called 'Proportional Load Sharing' [13, 14] in which system performance is enhanced by distributing the total active power in proportion to each generator's rated capacity. It is typically adopted in a system where there are multiple generators of different power capacities, so the load distribution is balanced effectively. Proportional Load Sharing is a widely used concept across disciplines like electrical engineering, computer systems, and network design. It refers to allocation of a total load (for instance, power, computational tasks, or network traffic) amongst multiple units based on capacity or other set parameters. That way, performance, efficiency, and reliability are improved since no single unit is overloaded while others stay dormant. In electrical systems, proportional load sharing is often used in parallel power sources like generators or uninterruptible power supplies (UPS). Each of the generators proportionally shares the total load. For example, if you have two generators, one rated for 40% and the other for 60% of the total capacity, then they will share the load in that exact ratio.

2. System Modeling

The generalized model of a an electrical power system is presented in Figure 1. From Figure 1, it is observed that, each generator is capable of delivering a certain rated power with the generator 1 (G1) having the capability of S_1 , generator 2 (G2) having the capability of S_2 , generator 3 (G3) having the capability of S_3 , generator 4 (G4) having the capability of S_4 . So, Total Generation capability maximum equals S in MVA.

$$S = S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4 \quad (1)$$

In terms of load demand, Load 1 (L1) load rating equals P_1 , Load 2 (L2) load rating equals P_2 , Load 3 (L3) load rating equals P_3 , Load 4 (L4) load rating equals P_4 , Load 5 (L5) load rating equals P_5 MVA. Hence, Total system load rating equals P MVA

$$P = P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + P_4 + P_5 \quad (2)$$

The generators must share the total load in proportion to their ratings. We need to calculate proportion capability (W_G) of each generator by considering total generators capabilities (S). Generator 1 (G1) percentage of proportion capability (W_{G1}) calculation.

$$W_{G1} = \frac{S_1 * 100}{S} \% \quad (3)$$

Generator 2 (G2) percentage of proportion capability (W_{G2}) calculation.

$$W_{G2} = \frac{S_2 * 100}{S} \% \quad (4)$$

Generator 3 (G3) percentage of proportion capability (W_{G3}) calculation.

$$W_{G3} = \frac{S_3 * 100}{S} \% \quad (5)$$

Figure 1. The description of example electrical power system

Generator 4 (G₄) percentage of proportion capability (W_{G4}) calculation.

$$W_{G4} = \frac{S_4 * 100}{S} \% \quad (6)$$

Now we understand percentage of proportion capability for each generator, and we can calculate amount of proportional load sharing (Y_G) for each generator.

Generator 1 (G₁) Proportional load sharing (Y_{G1}) calculation.

$$Y_{G1} = \frac{\frac{P * S_1 * 100}{S}}{100} = \frac{P * S_1 * 100}{100 * S} = \frac{P * S_1}{S} \quad (7)$$

Generator 2 (G₂) Proportional load sharing (Y_{G2}) calculation.

$$Y_{G2} = \frac{\frac{P * S_2 * 100}{S}}{100} = \frac{P * S_2 * 100}{100 * S} = \frac{P * S_2}{S} \quad (8)$$

Generator 3 (G₃) Proportional load sharing (Y_{G3}) calculation.

$$Y_{G3} = \frac{\frac{P * S_3 * 100}{S}}{100} = \frac{P * S_3 * 100}{100 * S} = \frac{P * S_3}{S} \quad (9)$$

Generator 4 (G₄) Proportional load sharing (Y_{G4}) calculation.

$$Y_{G4} = \frac{\frac{P * S_4 * 100}{S}}{100} = \frac{P * S_4 * 100}{100 * S} = \frac{P * S_4}{S} \quad (10)$$

For Step-load primitive calculations: it is necessary to monitor changes in power demand on the system, which is useful for load studies, system design, or for operational planning. In control systems, the term step response of a generator is used in the context of the generator responding to a sudden stepwise increase in load. So this analysis is crucial for answering dynamical questions such as the rate of change of the system, its responsiveness to change, its stability within these transitions. The initial reaction of a generator to a step increase load is an immediate drop in speed and frequency of the system (for synchronous generators). This accompanies Shared-Momentum

effect which acts with the inertial spin of the generator with the prime mover (turbine or engine). How quickly the generator regains frequency determines grid stability. Now amount of acceptable step load to be added to calculation for each generator for sudden change in load or total capability change. First, we attempt to measure the total step change in power ΔP for the Electrical Power Distribution System.

$$\Delta P = P_{new} - P_{old} \quad (11)$$

Amount of ΔP should be shared between online generators by considering generators step load capability.

3. Simulation Results

Simulation of system has been carried out by Python with Tkinter library in below. Fig.2 shows a graphical interface built using Python with Tkinter, that simulates proportional load sharing in a multi-generator power system.

Figure 2. Graphical interface simulating proportional load sharing in a multi-generator power system

The setup consists of four generators, G1-G4, with their rated capacities 15.0 MVA, 30.0 MVA, 45.0 MVA, and 60.0 MVA, respectively, all online and synchronized to a common busbar. In the bottom part of the picture, five loads are depicted (L1 to L5); these can be hooked up or disconnected via virtual circuit breakers. In the present simulation case, only L1 and L2 are activated, with the set values of load demand 50 MVA and 100 MVA, respectively, summing up to a 150 MVA total system load. This system load is shared equally among the generators depending on their rated capacities with respect to available power using proportional load sharing with all of the generators online. This corresponds with the previously defined load allocation logic considering generator output limits. The output section at the right side of the interface presents the calculated allocation sharing for each of the generators: G1 with a 10 percent (15 MVA) contribution, G2 with 20 percent (30 MVA), G3 with 30 percent (45 MVA), and G4 with 40 percent (60 MVA), which in total fulfill the overall system demand. Also, the control panel

contains fields where users may change the values of generator limits and loads, and thus alter several operational scenarios with respect to the simulation model. In addition, two buttons, 'Reload' and 'Clear Output', refresh the results of the simulations and reset the output shown on the interface respectively. This proportional load sharing interface fulfills functionality in the load sharing theory education by allowing a user to practically visualize the interplay between generator coordination, real-time load distribution, and system response to different loading and generation scenarios—system states during transitions—over time.

Conclusion

In this paper a thorough case study of proportional load sharing is presented in a multi-generator environment. A simulation model is created in Python using Tkinter to illustrate how generators actually participate in foisting varying loads and demand on the system according to their rating. The interface allows users to change the values of generator capacities and the extent of the network so that the behavior of the system can be monitored immediately. The results obtained verify that in systems with appropriate supporting generators, power distribution, and proportional load sharing, overloading avoided.

References

- [1]. Park, C.; Wang, M.; Alotaibi, R.M.; Rezk, H. Load-Sharing Model under Lindley Distribution and Its Parameter Estimation Using the Expectation-Maximization Algorithm. *Entropy* 2020, 22, 1329. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e22111329>
- [2]. He, W., Yu, M. & Yu, J. Distributed finite-time active power sharing control with generation costs considered. *SN Appl. Sci.* 1, 1692 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-019-1745-0>
- [3]. Abdullah, Mahmoud, A. M. Al-Quteimat, O.O. Ushkarenko, and Atia AlHawamleh, "Improving the Accuracy of the Active Power Load Sharing in Paralleled Generators in the Presence of Drive Motors Shaft Speed Instability," *International Journal of Electronics and Telecommunications*, pp. 371–377, Jul. 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.24425/ijet.2021.137822>
- [4]. Nebey, A.H. Automatic load sharing of distribution transformer for overload protection. *BMC Res Notes* 13, 17 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-019-4880-1>
- [5]. Taha, M.Q.; Kurnaz, S. Droop Control Optimization for Improved Power Sharing in AC Islanded Microgrids Based on Centripetal Force Gravity Search Algorithm. *Energies* 2023, 16, 7953. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16247953>
- [6]. Rohmingtluanga, C.; Datta, S.; Sinha, N.; Ustun, T.S.; Kalam, A. ANFIS-Based Droop Control of an AC Microgrid System: Considering Intake of Water Treatment Plant. *Energies* 2022, 15, 7442. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15197442>
- [7]. Sun, Y., Hou, X., Yang, J., Han, H., Su, M., & Guerrero, J. M. (2017). New Perspectives on Droop Control in AC MicroGrid. *I E E E Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 64(7), 5741 - 5745. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2017.2677328>
- [8]. E. Yusubov and L. Bekirova, "Adaptive Metaheuristic Moth-Flame Optimized Droop Control Method for DC Microgrids," 2022 International Conference Automatics and Informatics (ICAI), Varna, Bulgaria, 2022, pp. 204-209, doi: 10.1109/ICAI55857.2022.9960119.
- [9]. D. Cardoso da S., J. S. Dohler, P. M. d. Almeida and J. G. d. Oliveira, "Droop Control for Power Sharing and Voltage and Frequency Regulation in Parallel Distributed Generations on AC Microgrid," 2018 13th IEEE International Conference on Industry Applications (INDUSCON), Sao Paulo, Brazil, 2018, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/INDUSCON.2018.8627328. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8627328>

[10]. E. Yusubov and L. Bekirova, "A Standalone Dc Microgrid Energy Management Strategy Using The Battery State Of Charge," *Informatyka Automatyka Pomiary w Gospodarce i Ochronie Środowiska*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 75–78, Sep. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.35784/iapgos.5320> .

[11]. K. G. Ravikumar, B. Bosley, T. Clark and J. Garcia, "Isochronous load sharing principles for an islanded system with steam and gas turbine generators," 2017 Petroleum and Chemical Industry Technical Conference (PCIC), Calgary, AB, Canada, 2017, pp. 405-412, doi: 10.1109/PCICON.2017.8188761. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8188761>

[12]. K. Gubba Ravikumar, B. Bosley, T. Clark and J. Garcia, "Generation Control System: Using Isochronous Load-Sharing Principles With Gas and Steam Turbine Generators," in *IEEE Industry Applications Magazine*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 36-44, March-April 2019, doi: 10.1109/MIAS.2018.2875127. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8581587>

[13]. A. Aggarwal, A. S. Siddiqui and S. Mishra, "Proportional Load Sharing in an Autonomous Hybrid Micro-grid Using Interlinking Converter," 2022 IEEE International Conference on Power Electronics, Smart Grid, and Renewable Energy (PESGRE), Trivandrum, India, 2022, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/PESGRE52268.2022.9715826. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9715826>

[14]. X. Zhao and L. Yang, "An Improved Droop Control Method to Improve Bus Voltage and Ensure Accurate Proportional Load Power Sharing in Isolated DC Microgrids," 2020 12th IEEE PES Asia-Pacific Power and Energy Engineering Conference (APPEEC), Nanjing, China, 2020, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/APPEEC48164.2020.9220337. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9220337>

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